

Micellar Effects upon the Acid Hydrolysis of *N-p*-Chlorophenylbenzohydroxamic Acid

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The micellar catalysis of organic reactions has been widely studied in recent years¹. A voluminous literature concerns the kinetics and mechanisms of hydrolysis of esters, amides, anilides in the presence of surfactants. Surprisingly, limited work has been reported on micellar catalysis of hydroxamic acid², despite the recent impressive developments of these compounds in diverse fields³. This prompted us to undertake the present investigation on acidic hydrolysis of *N-p*-chlorophenylbenzohydroxamic acid (Cl.C₆H₄N(OH).(C=O).C₆H₅) in the presence of two cationic surfactant cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), cetylpyridinium chloride (CPC) and one anionic surfactant sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS) in aquo-dioxane media.

Results and Discussion

Both anionic and cationic surfactants give a rate inhibition and the results are shown in Table 1. The variation of rate constant with [surfactant] is generally treated on the assumption that substrate S, is distributed between the aqueous and micellar pseudo-phase (Scheme 1) and can react in each pseudo-phase, with the first order rate constants being k_w and k_m .

Scheme 1

The micellised surfactant (detergent) is designated as D_n , and its concentration is that of the total surfactant concentration, less than that of monomeric surfactant ($[D_n] = [D_T] - \text{cmc}$). The concentration of monomeric surfactant should be the critical micelle concentration (cmc) under kinetic conditions. K_s is the equilibrium for substrate binding. This model (Scheme 1) leads to the relationship,

$$\frac{1}{k_w - k_{\psi}} = \frac{1}{k_w - k_m} + \left(\frac{1}{k_w - k_m} \right) \left(\frac{N}{K_s([D_T] - \text{cmc})} \right)$$

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF SURFACTANTS ON THE HYDROLYSIS OF *N-p*-Cl-PBHA AT 65° IN 0.76 M HCl

[Surfactant] × 10 ³ M	× 10 ⁵ k_w s ⁻¹		
	CTAB	CPC	SLS
0	5.67	5.67	5.67
0.175	5.56	5.70	3.53
0.350	5.57	—	3.25
0.50	—	—	3.18
0.70	5.65	5.29	3.04
0.86	—	5.04	2.48
1.04	—	—	1.85
1.40	5.53	4.75	—
2.50	5.14	4.59	—
3.50	—	—	—
5.00	4.83	4.42	—
6.85	4.54	4.20	—
9.60	3.82	3.84	—
12.5	2.76	2.48	—
15.0	2.61	2.07	—
20.5	2.39	1.75	—
24.6	2.23	—	—
50.0	1.78	1.46	—

in which k_{ψ} is the observed pseudo-first order rate constant and N is the micellar aggregation number. The substrate is not soluble in water. Therefore, we used 20% (v/v) dioxane-water media and high temperature which slightly attenuate the micellar rate effects. The cmc is determined from a graph of pseudo-first order observed rate constant versus surfactant concentration; the break in the curve is taken as 'the kinetic cmc'. From the plot of $1/(k_w - k_{\psi})$ versus $1/([D_T] - \text{cmc})$ it is possible to calculate K_s and k_m . Good linear relationship resulted for the data in Table 1. The values for the parameters in Table 2 were obtained by least-

TABLE 2—PARAMETERS FOR THE MICELLAR HYDROLYSIS OF *N-p*-Cl-PBHA

	D_T range	K_s/N	Correlation coefficient
CTAB	0.00500–0.0125	515.3	0.900
CPC	0.00250–0.0125	539.5	0.938
SLS	0.000175–0.000520	36507.0	0.801

squares treatment. Since the experimental conditions were identical for the com-pound, the value of N will be the same; therefore, K_s is proportional to K_s/N values. It is evident from Table 2, that the substrate is strongly bounded to micelles (high values of K_s). In micellar-inhibited reactions, as most of the reactions take place in the bulk aqueous phase, the rate constant for the reaction on the micellar phase (k_m) is nearly zero. The continuous decrease in the rate constants with increase in

surfactant concentration also supports that $k_m \approx 0$. If we compare the extent of inhibition of different surfactants, the order is SLS >CPC >CTAB. The studies could not be carried at higher concentration of SLS owing to the interference observed in colorimetric method for determining the hydroxamic acid. The greater inhibition effect of SLS is probably because bonding between an anionic head-group and the hydronium ion reduces its effective acidity. One of the important factors for reactions in micellar environment is the orientation effect in which the micelle attracts the neutral substrate and a reagent, such as H_3O^+ , of charge opposite to the charge of micelle. The other factor is micellar stabilisation of a transition state of charge opposite to that of micelle relative to its stabilisation of the reagent, in turn relative to stabilisation by water, leading to rate inhibition.

Although the detergent effects do not change markedly with temperature the activation enthalpy and entropy is affected by surfactants (Table 3). The values of ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger are typical for bimolecular reaction. Addition of micelles of NaLS, CTAB and CPC, leads to an increase in the ΔH^\ddagger because of unfavourable electrostatic interaction and there is also slight decrease in the ΔS^\ddagger .

Experimental

N-p-Cl-Phenylbenzohydroxamic acid was prepared by standard method⁴. The acids used were of analytical reagent grade. Dioxane (B.D.H.,

TABLE 3—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE HYDROLYSIS OF *N-p*-Cl-PBHA

Parameter*	CTAB			CPC			SLS			
	0.0	$1.40 \times 10^3 M$	$12.3 \times 10^3 M$	$20.5 \times 10^3 M$	$1.40 \times 10^3 M$	$9.60 \times 10^3 M$	$20.9 \times 10^3 M$	$0.175 \times 10^3 M$	$0.520 \times 10^3 M$	$0.867 \times 10^3 M$
ΔH^\ddagger	39.2	64.0	75.2	83.1	72.0	68.9	91.4	60.2	64.7	67.3
ΔS^\ddagger	-213	-138	-109	-87	-114	-125	-64	-152	-140	-134
ΔG^\ddagger	102.7	105.1	107.5	109.0	105.9	106.1	110.0	105.3	106.3	107.2
Correlation coefficient	0.999	0.999	0.958	0.981	0.972	0.973	0.952	0.972	0.991	0.985

ΔH^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger , kJ mol⁻¹; ΔS^\ddagger , JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹.

A.R.) was used as such. The iron(III) chloride solution used in the colorimetric procedure was prepared by dissolving anhydrous ferric(III) chloride (S.M., LR; 44 g) of distilled water (1 dm³) containing concentrated HCl (10 ml). CTAB (E. Merck), CPC (Loba) and NaLS (Loba) were used as such.

Kinetic measurements were made using the spectrophotometric method (EC 5700 A spectrophotometer). The reaction kinetics were followed by measuring the concentration of the hydroxamic acids by the colour reaction with Fe^{III} ions. An aliquot (2.0 ml) of the reaction mixture was periodically removed, ferric chloride solution (2 ml) was added to it and the resulting solution was diluted to 10 ml and its absorbance determined. Beer's law is obeyed by the system.

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References

1. C. A. BUNTON, S. WRIGHT, P. M. HOLLAND and F. NOME, *Langmuir*, 1993, **9**, 117; K. A. WILK and B. BUREZYK, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1989, **93**, 8219; T. J. BROXTON, J. R. CHRISTIE and X. SANGO, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1987, **52**, 4814; A. BLASKO, C. A. BUNTON, Y. S. HONG, M. M. MHALA, J. R. MOFFAT and S. WRIGHT, *J. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1991, **4**, 618; C. A. BUNTON, F. NOME, F. H. QUINA and L. ROMSTED, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1991, **24**, 357.
2. D. C. BERNDT, N. UTRAPIROMSUK and D. E. CONRAN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1984, **49**, 106; D. C. BERNDT, J. E. ANGUS, M. J. WOOD, R. F. ATKINSON, T. A. QURESHI, B. J. SHAY and A. I. PROVANCHER, *Int. J. Chem. Kinetics*, 1989, **21**, 431; D. C. BERNDT, N. UTRAPIROMSUK and S. S. JAGLAN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1979, **44**, 136; D. C. BERNDT, Z. HE and M. E. AYOUB, *Int. J. Chem. Kinetics*, 1992, **24**, 695.
3. L. S. ROMSTED in "Micellization, Solubilization and Microemulsions", ed. K. L. MITTAL, Plenum Press, New York, 1977, Vol. 2, p. 509; L. S. ROMSTED in "Surfactants in Solution", eds. K. L. MITTAL and B. LINDMAN, Plenum Press, New York, 1984, Vol. 2, p. 1015; C. A. BUNTON and G. SAVELLI, "Advanced Physical Organic Heterogeneous Systems", eds. M. GRATZEL and K. KALYANASUNDARAM, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1991.
4. U. PRIYADARSHINI and S. G. TANDON, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1967, **12** 143.

